

Biomimetic mineralization of CaCO_3 , TbCO_3 and Ca-TbCO_3 mediated by HEDTA and β -CD

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Abstract : Growth morphology of calcium carbonate, terbium carbonate and their mixed metal carbonates have been investigated in presence of organic additives namely *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine-*N,N,N'*-triacetic acid (HEDTA) and β -cyclodextrin (β -CD). Rhombohedral calcite phase of calcium carbonate transformed to elongated hexagonal tabular morphology by the cooperative influence of HEDTA and β -CD. Further, flower-like, leaf-like complex morphologies of amorphous TbCO_3 and Ca-TbCO_3 resulted with the influence of the above both additives. Scanning Electron Microscopy, X-ray diffraction, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy have been used to characterize the products. The photoluminescence (PL) measurements of TbCO_3 showed a green emission at 490 to 580 nm.

Keywords : Morphology, calcium carbonate, terbium carbonate, photoluminescence.

Introduction

Controlled production of inorganic structures with tailored morphologies via biomimetic routes has received much attention because of their enhanced performance and properties^{1,2}. Some of the tools used to generate advanced materials are application of templates, soluble additives as crystallization modifiers, inhibitors and nucleating agents³. Biomimetic synthesis is an eco-friendly route for the production of materials with controlled morphologies³. Calcium carbonate has been extensively studied as model compound for biomimetic mineralization⁴ since it is an excellent example for demonstrating a wide variety of morphologies from single crystal to polycrystalline. Calcium carbonate occurs in three crystalline polymorphs i.e. calcite, vaterite, aragonite and two hydrated crystal forms i.e. calcium carbonate monohydrate, calcium carbonate hexahydrate in addition to amorphous phase. Calcium carbonate is used in biomedical fields^{5,6} such as drug delivery, treatment of dry eye etc. in addition to its use in coatings, plastics, alloys and catalysts. Like calcium carbonate, terbium carbonate also exhibits different morphologies⁷. Due to its strong green emitting property, it is used in fluorescence lamps and biosensors^{8,9}.

Use of organic additives with carboxylic acid functional groups for directing the phase and morphology of

calcium carbonate is well documented¹⁰⁻¹³. In addition to the organic compounds, polysaccharides such as cyclodextrins also find use as crystal growth modifier^{14,15}. In nature, living organisms use a complex organic matrix comprising of soluble and insoluble components to control the size, shape, orientation, texture and assembly of biominerals¹⁶. Hence we have studied the biomimetic production of CaCO_3 , TbCO_3 and Ca-TbCO_3 by the combined influence of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine-*N,N,N'*-triacetic acid (HEDTA) and β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) as crystal growth modifiers.

Results and discussion

Morphology :

In this biomimetic mineralization, the individual and combined influence of HEDTA and β -CD on CaCO_3 , TbCO_3 and Ca-TbCO_3 was examined. We carried out biomimetic study by using different metal to additive ratios ([metal]/[additive] = 100, 50, 10, 7.7, 5.0, 1.0, 0.5 and 0.33). No crystals appeared at metal to additive ratios of 1, 0.5 and 0.33 in presence of HEDTA. The probable reason for this may be higher ligand concentration and very low pH (3.0). In case of β -CD alone and mixed components of HEDTA and β -CD, we could not proceed for crystallization at the above mentioned metal to addi-

tive ratios of 1.0, 0.5 and 0.33 due to insolubility of β -CD. Based on the above observations, good results were obtained when metal to additive ratio was 10 at solution pH around 6.5–7.0. As shown in Fig. 1, regular rhombohedra of calcite phase of calcium carbonate resulted in control experiments i.e. without addition of organic additives such as HEDTA or β -CD (Fig. 1a). In presence of HEDTA and β -CD alone, no apparent change in the morphology was observed. But a decrease in the size of rhombohedra from 30–40 μm to 10–15 μm was recorded (Fig. 1b and 1c). With the cooperative influence of HEDTA and β -CD together, rhombohedral calcite transformed to elongated hexagonal tabular-like calcite with 20–50 μm size (Fig. 1d). No major changes in the crystal habit were observed except a decrease in the crystal size when the additive concentration i.e. metal to additive ratios was increased to 7.7 and 5.0, respectively (Fig. 2).

Similarly, we examined the growth morphology of TbCO_3 . As shown in Fig. 3, flake-like structure of TbCO_3 was observed in control experiments. A dense flake-like morphology of TbCO_3 transformed to small flower-bud morphology in presence of HEDTA (Fig. 3b), porous films in presence of β -CD (Fig. 3c) and a cauliflower-like morphology in presence of both HEDTA and β -CD (Fig. 3d).

Further, based on the above two systems, we examined the mineralization of mixed metal carbonates with calcium and terbium in presence of HEDTA and β -CD. Amorphous porous structures of Ca-TbCO_3 resulted in presence of HEDTA (Fig. 4a). In presence of β -CD, alovera leaf-like structure of Ca-TbCO_3 formed (Fig. 4b). But with the cooperative influence of both HEDTA and β -CD, flower-like structures of Ca-TbCO_3 appeared (Fig. 4c). Presence of both Ca (1.0 wt%) and Tb (58.0 wt%)

Fig. 1. SEM images of CaCO_3 : (a) produced in control experiments, (b) in presence of HEDTA, (c) in presence of β -CD and (d) in presence of both HEDTA and β -CD.

Fig. 2. SEM images of CaCO_3 in presence of both HEDTA and β -CD at metal to additive ratios : (a) $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{additive}] = 7.7$ and (b) $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{additive}] = 5.0$.

was clearly evident from EDAX analysis of Ca-TbCO_3 (Fig. 4d). Amorphous powder was obtained when the additive concentration i.e. metal to additive ratios was increased to 7.7 and 5.0, respectively (Fig. 5).

X-Ray diffraction analysis :

Fig. 6 shows the powdered XRD patterns of the metal carbonates. The peaks at 23.12, 29.44, 31.47, 36.03, 36.58, 39.70, 43.21, 45.10, 48.15, 56.61, 60.71, and 69.19 confirmed the formation of calcite phase of CaCO_3 with the cooperative influence of HEDTA and β -CD (Fig. 6(i)). The straight lines in powder XRD patterns for TbCO_3 and Ca-TbCO_3 indicated the formation of amorphous phases of minerals (Fig. 6(ii) and 6(iii)).

FT-IR analysis :

Phase composition of the CaCO_3 , TbCO_3 and Ca-

TbCO_3 , has been determined through FT-IR measurements. FT-IR spectra of CaCO_3 polymorphs displays characteristic absorption bands corresponding to the C-O bond vibrations, namely, symmetric stretching (ν_1), out-of-plane bending (ν_2), a doubly degenerate asymmetric stretching (ν_3) and a doubly degenerate in-plane bending (ν_4)¹⁷. In CaCO_3 sample spectrum, the vibration bands at 712.35 and 871.30 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the ν_4 and ν_2 modes of calcite CO_3^{2-} (Fig. 7). In TbCO_3 sample spectrum, the vibration bands at 748.83 and 845.84 cm^{-1} indicate ν_4 and ν_2 modes of CO_3^{2-} . For Ca-TbCO_3 , since TbCO_3 is a major phase in mixed metal carbonates, we observed vibration modes similar to TbCO_3 .

Photoluminescence :

In general lanthanide elements exhibits photoluminescence property due to involvement of 4f orbitals. The photoluminescence properties of TbCO_3 was examined. TbCO_3 emits the green emission corresponding to the transitions $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_6$, $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_5$ and $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_4$ at 490, 545 and 580 nm, respectively on photo excitation at 360 nm (Fig. 8).

Growth mechanism of calcium carbonate :

Mann⁴ and Smith *et al.*¹⁸, suggested that the soluble acidic macromolecules absorb onto the surface of the insoluble crystal matrix and play an important role in controlling the selectivity and crystal morphology of polymorph during the process of mineralization. Similarly, polysaccharides such as β -CD a cyclic oligosaccharide, which is a truncated canonical molecule with hollow cavity constructed by seven glycopyranoside units, also controls the mineral morphology during biomimetic crystallization^{14,15}. We examined the combined influence of HEDTA and β -CD on crystal growth. Rhombohedral calcite crystals containing {104} faces were obtained in the control experiments. No significant influence was observed on the morphology of calcite by either HEDTA or β -CD. But a new shape evaluation process of “rhombohedral-to-hexagonal tabular” was observed by the cooperative influence of HEDTA and β -CD. A new guest-host complex might have formed by mixing the HEDTA and β -CD. In this, complex tricarboxylate organic molecule (HEDTA) acts as a binding part and β -CD act as solvating part similar to the mechanism proposed for elongated calcite crystals by the influence of β -CD-b-PLGA copolymer by

Fig. 3. SEM images of TbCO₃ : (a) produced in control experiments, (b) in presence of HEDTA, (c) in presence of β-CD and (d) in presence of both HEDTA and β-CD.

Fig. 4. SEM images of Ca-TbCO₃ : (a) in presence of HEDTA, (b) in presence of β-CD, (c) in presence of both HEDTA and β-CD and (d) EDAX spectrum of Ca-TbCO₃.

Fig. 5. SEM images of Ca-TbCO_3 produced in presence of both HEDTA and β -CD at metal to additive ratios : (a) $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{additive}] = 7.7$ and (b) $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{additive}] = 5.0$.

Fig. 6. Powder XRD patterns of compounds produced in presence of both HEDTA and β -cyclodextrin : (i) CaCO_3 , (ii) TbCO_3 and (iii) Ca-TbCO_3 (c=calcite).

Fig. 7. FT-IR spectra of CaCO_3 , TbCO_3 and Ca-TbCO_3 produced in the presence of both HEDTA and β -CD.

Fig. 8. Photoluminescence spectrum of TbCO_3 .

Zhu *et al.*¹⁴. We suggest a probable binding of this complex on growing surface of calcite along *c*-axis. The rhombohedral crystals become progressively truncated towards the $\{001\}$ face and eventually resulted in hexagonal tabular crystals.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NaHCO_3 were obtained from Merck, *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine-*N,N,N'*-triacetic acid (HEDTA) and $\text{TbCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and Acros Organics, respectively. β -Cyclodextrin was purchased from Himedia Chemicals.

Synthesis :

In a typical experiment, at room temperature, 0.0278 g HEDTA (0.1 mmol) was taken along with the 0.147 g $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.0 mmol) in a 25 ml glass beaker contain-

ing 10 ml water and stirred for 10 min. To the above solution, 0.084 g NaHCO₃ (1.0 mmol) was added with constant stirring for few minutes and the final solution was kept for crystallization. After 24 h the crystals appeared were filtered, washed with distilled water and dried in a desiccator. For the synthesis of terbium carbonate, 0.0374 g TbCl₃.6H₂O (1.0 mmol) was used in place of CaCl₂.2H₂O. In case of mixed metal carbonates, 0.0187 g TbCl₃.6H₂O (0.05 mmol) and 0.0735 g CaCl₂.2H₂O (0.05 mmol) was used. Crystallization of metal carbonates in presence of β-CD was carried out by taking 0.1136 g β-CD (0.1 mmol) instead of HEDTA. To test the cooperative influence of both additives, 0.1136 g β-CD (0.1 mmol) and 0.0278 g HEDTA (0.1 mmol) were mixed in place of single additive.

Characterisation methods :

The morphology of the obtained compounds was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using FEI Quanta 200 FEG with EDS. Powder X-ray diffraction pattern was recorded by using "PANALYTICAL X'Pert pro Powder X-ray diffractometer" with graphite monochromatic CuK_α (λ = 1.5406 Å) radiation at room temperature. IR spectrum was measured using KBr pellet preparation method on Perkin-Elmer "spectrum two FT-IR" system.

Conclusions

In summary, individual and cooperative influence of HEDTA and β-CD on biomimetic growth of CaCO₃, TbCO₃ and Ca-TbCO₃ have been investigated. Elongated hexagonal tabular crystals of calcite and flower like complex morphologies of amorphous TbCO₃ and Ca-TbCO₃ resulted with cooperative influence of HEDTA and β-CD. TbCO₃ emits green emission under photo excitation.

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